

Studies on Insecticides and Fungicides. Part I. Preparation of Some Acetoxymercury Derivatives of 3-Substituted $\alpha\alpha$ -Bis-(4-hydroxyphenyl)- $\beta\beta$ -trichloroethane

(Miss) M. Nandi, S. D. Verma, J. K. Mehrotra, and A. K. Sircar

Azo derivatives of bis-4-hydroxyphenyl- $\beta\beta$ -trichloroethane have been prepared as potential fungicides and insecticides. These compounds and some others, structurally similar to D. D. T., have been mercurated and estimated for their mercury contents.

With the object of finding out organic compounds, which are both insecticides and fungicides, additional functional groups have been introduced in $\alpha\alpha$ -bis-(4-hydroxyphenyl)- $\beta\beta$ -trichloroethane¹. In the present work, this compound has been coupled with the diazotised solution of a number of aromatic amines in equimolecular proportions. The choice has been so made that either a phenolic or a nitro, or a sulphonic acid group is also introduced. Compounds possessing these groups are known to exhibit fungicidal activity. In Table I are recorded the coupled compounds.

Salts of heavy metals as well as organo-metallic compounds, specially copper salts² and organic mercurals³, have long been found of practical use in control of seed-borne and soil-borne fungus diseases of plants. Even simple alkyl and aryl compounds of mercury are more reactive as bactericides and fungicides⁴ than inorganic salts. The volatility of organic mercurals is an important factor in the choice of disinfectants, where penetration or coating is required, in order that the parasitic fungus may be acted upon. We have therefore prepared organo-mercury compounds of $\alpha\alpha$ -bis-(4-hydroxy-, 4-methoxy-, and 2-methoxy-4-hydroxy-phenyl)- $\beta\beta$ -trichloroethanes and also some of the compounds recorded in Table I. In order to ascertain the positions of the four acetoxymercury groups entered in $\alpha\alpha$ -bis-(4-hydroxyphenyl)- $\beta\beta$ -trichloroethane, the organo-mercury compound was first demercurated by bromine and then converted into the corresponding bis-dibromoethylene derivative by treatment with ethanolic KOH. This on oxidation with chromic acid gave bis-(3,5-dibromo-4-hydroxy)benzophenone⁵, indicating that the acetoxymercury groups had entered in positions 3, 5, 3', 5'. The positions of the acetoxymercury in other compounds have been suggested as being the most possible one on theoretical considerations and on the basis of the above results. Further work on the structure of these compounds is in progress. The biological activity of these compounds is also under study and the results will be published elsewhere.

1. Ter Meer, *Ber.*, 1874, 7, 1201.

2. Martin, *J. Appl. Biol.*, 1932, 19, 98; Masson, *J. Agr. Prat.*, 1897, i, 51, 914.

3. Schonhofer and Borirath, U.S.P. 1987372/1934; Deskaie, U.S.P. 2369339/1945.

4. Guha Sircar *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 367, 636; 1951, 28, 80; Bond and Nolan, *Amer. J. Trop. Med. Hyg.*, 1954, 3, 187.

5. Baeyer, *Annalen*, 1880, 202, 131.

EXPERIMENTAL

αα-Bis-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-βββ-trichloroethane.—To an intimate mixture of phenol (5.6 g.) and chloral hydrate (5.0 g.), cooled to 20°, a cooled mixture (12 g.) of H₂SO₄ (conc.) and acetic acid (1:1) was slowly added. The whole was kept in an ice bath for 6 to 8 hours and then poured on cold water (500 ml). The rose-red product was filtered, dissolved in dilute ethanol, and decolorised. The clear solution furnished a white product (8 g.) which after several recrystallisations from dilute ethanol melted at 202° (lit. m. p. 202°). (Found: Cl, 33.59. Calc. for C₁₄H₁₁O₄Cl₃: Cl, 33.54%). Acetic anhydride furnished *αα-bis-(4-acetoxyphe-nyl)-βββ-trichloroethane*, m. p. 142° (lit. m. p. 138°). (Found: Cl, 26.67. Calc. for C₁₈H₁₅O₄Cl₃: Cl, 26.52%). Lauryl chloride furnished *αα-bis-(4-lauryloxyphenyl)-βββ-trichloroethane*, m. p. 72°. (Found: Cl, 15.41. C₃₆H₇₃O₄Cl₃ requires Cl, 15.63%).

αα-Bis-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-βββ-trichloroethane (2 g.) was mercurated by heating for 7 to 8 hours with mercuric acetate (9 g.) in acetic acid, yielding a pale yellow product, *αα-bis-(3,5-thiacetoxymercuri-4-hydroxyphenyl)-βββ-trichloroethane* (8 g.) which was filtered and washed with boiling water till free of mercury ions. (Found: Hg, 59.92. C₂₂H₁₉O₁₀Cl₃-Hg₄ requires Hg, 59.35%). The mercurated product (6.4 g.) was suspended in glacial acetic acid with KBr. (3 g.). To the hot solution bromine (3.2 g.) in glacial acetic acid (40 ml) was added. When whole of the substance had dissolved, the mixture was poured on water where a light brown product, *αα-bis-(3,5-dibromo-4-hydroxyphenyl)-βββ-trichloroethane* (2.75 g.) separated which was filtered and washed free of bromine; m. p. 85° (Found: Br, 50.18. C₁₄H₇O₂Cl₃Br₄ requires Br, 50.53%). The bromo derivative (6.3 g.) in dry ethanol was heated for 15 mns. with ethanolic KOH (1.6 g.). The dark coloured solution was cooled and neutralised with dilute acetic acid, providing a white precipitate (5.8 g.) which was filtered and washed with water. *αα-Bis-(3,5-dibromo-4-hydroxyphenyl)-dichloroethylene*, which changed to light yellow on standing, melted at 78°. (Found: Br, 53.23. C₁₄H₆O₂Cl₂Br₄ requires Br, 53.52%). The dibromoethylene compound (3 g.) was oxidised by heating with chromic acid to *bis-(3,5-dibromo-4-hydroxy)-benzophenone* (2.1 g.); m. p. 225-26° (lit. m. p. 225-26°). (Found: Br, 60.82. Calc. for C₁₃H₆O₃Br₄: Br, 60.38%). The phenylhydrazone m. p. 285°.

αα-Bis-(4-methoxyphenyl)-βββ-trichloroethane.—Rose-red, m. p. 91° (lit. m. p. 89°, 92°); yield 82%. (Found: Cl, 31.16. Calc. for C₁₆H₁₃O₂Cl₃: Cl, 30.82%).

αα-Bis-(2-methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl)-βββ-trichloroethane.—Slightly brown; m. p. 98° (lit. m. p. 98°). (Found: Cl, 28.47. Calc. for C₁₆H₁₅O₄Cl₃: Cl, 28.21%).

The two preceding compounds were prepared by the method described above, using anisole and resorcinol monomethyl ether respectively.

The above compounds and compounds 1, 3, and 4 in Table I were mercurated with an excess of mercury acetate by the method used for *αα-bis-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-βββ-trichloroethane*. The results are shown in Table II.

α-(4'-Hydroxyphenyl)-α-(3-azo-X-4-hydroxyphenyl)-βββ-trichloroethane (X=O, *m*- & *p*-nitro; *o*-hydroxy; *p*-sulphonic acid).—An equimolecular quantity of the amino compound was diazotised in the usual manner and coupled in cold with *αα-bis-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-βββ-trichloroethane* in acetic acid solution. The coupled product was recrystallised from dilute ethanol. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Compound (R=).	M.P.	Colour.	Yield.	Found.	Reqd.
1	-N=N-o-C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂	170°	Yellow	80%	C : 60.86 H : 2.00 N : 9.23 Cl : 22.07	51.45 2.98 9.00 22.84
2	-N=N-m-C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂	175°	Mustard-yellow	74	C : 59.82 H : 3.12 N : 9.31 Cl : 22.51	51.45 2.98 9.00 22.84
3	-N=N-p-C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂	190°	Yellow	80	C : 51.33 H : 2.52 N : 8.74 Cl : 22.43	51.45 2.98 9.00 22.84
4	-N=N-o-C ₆ H ₄ OH	157°	Light brown	79	C : 54.28 H : 3.12 N : 6.67 Cl : 24.92	54.85 3.45 5.40 24.34
5	-N=N-p-C ₆ H ₄ SO ₃ H	194°	Yellowish white	67	C : 47.24 H : 2.32 N : 5.98 Cl : 21.67	47.86 2.99 5.60 21.24

TABLE II

No.	Compound mercurated.	% Yield	%Hg.		Representing HgO.COMe	
			Found.	Reqd.	No.	groups position.
1	R(X=H)	96	59.92	59.35	4	5,5,3',5'
2	R'(X=H)	95	58.30	58.15	4	3,5,3',5'
3	R''(X=H)	95	58.49	58.83	4	3,5,3'-5'
4	R-N=N-o-C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂	94	57.67	57.00	5	5,3',5',4',6''
5	R-N=N-p-C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂	94	57.61	57.00	5	5,3',5',3'',6''
6	R-N=N-o-C ₆ H ₄ OH	92	58.43	57.97	5	5,3',5',3'',5''